

SCHOOL HEADS' LEADERSHIP STYLES: ITS RELATIONSHIP TO CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the leadership styles of 76 secondary school heads in special education in the Schools Division of Camarines Norte (SY 2023–2024) and their relation to SPED challenges and opportunities. Findings show that school heads commonly practice collaborative and supportive leadership but need stronger assertive leadership and advocacy for SPED. Major challenges include limited resources, training, funding, and policy support, while strong leadership commitment promotes inclusive practices. Leadership style alone was not significantly related to SPED challenges and opportunities, suggesting other contextual factors play a bigger role. The study recommends targeted leadership training, improved resource allocation and policies, stronger support systems, adoption of an intervention plan, and further research to enhance inclusive education.

Keywords: *School head, Leadership style, Challenges, Opportunities, Special Education*

INTRODUCTION

Effective leadership plays a crucial role in ensuring the success of special education programs. School heads serve as key figures in promoting inclusive practices, allocating resources, and inspiring teachers to meet the diverse needs of learners with disabilities. Under Republic Act No. 9155 (Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001), school heads are required to set the mission and vision of the school, create a learning

environment that supports all learners, develop school programs, and offer educational programs, projects, and services that provide equitable opportunities for all learners in the community. Moreover, the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) emphasizes that school leaders must be learner-centered, build and strengthen stakeholder networks, and foster an inclusive school culture that accommodates diverse needs.

Despite existing policies supporting inclusive education, many schools continue to encounter challenges such as limited funding, lack of trained personnel, and inadequate facilities. Conversely, opportunities exist for school heads to innovate, collaborate with stakeholders, and strengthen programs that promote accessibility and equity in education. This study, titled “School Heads’ Leadership Styles in Special Education: Its Relationship to Challenges and Opportunities,” aimed to determine the leadership Style used by secondary school heads, identify the challenges and opportunities encountered in implementing special education, examine the relationship between leadership styles and these factors, and propose an intervention program to address identified gaps.

The findings of this study served as the basis of the **Innovative interventions for SPED Leadership Implementation**, an intervention plan to address the challenges and enhance the implementation of SPED program in the division.

Research Questions

1. What are the leadership styles utilized by secondary school heads in promoting and managing special education programs?
2. What are the challenges encountered by school heads in the implementation of special education?
3. What are the opportunities associated with school leadership in special education?
4. How do the different leadership styles in special education relate to the challenges and opportunities encountered by the school heads?
5. What intervention may be proposed to address the challenges in the implementation of special education?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to achieve its objectives. According to Lappe (2000), descriptive–correlational research is suitable when the objective is to explore associations between variables as they naturally occur in real-world settings, particularly in educational research. Similarly, Wherry (2014) explained that correlational analysis is effective in identifying the degree and direction of relationships among variables, making it appropriate for studies that seek to understand how leadership styles relate to organizational outcomes. The study involved seventy-one (76) school heads from public secondary schools who served as respondents. They represented various leadership designations such as officers-in-charge, teachers-in-charge, head teachers, and principals.

Data were gathered using Leadership Style Questionnaire developed by Centenary College Louisiana and to assess the challenges, opportunities, and intervention plans related to the implementation of special education administered a researcher-made survey as the second and third sections of the questionnaire. Following data collection, descriptive statistics were used to calculate, describe, and summarize the data in a logical and efficient manner, as elucidated by Vetter (2017).

The study employed correlation analysis to describe the relationship between school leadership styles and the challenges and opportunities in special education. According to Wherry (2014), correlation analysis is a valuable tool for determining the strength and direction of relationships between two continuous variables. This statistical method assessed the correlation between specific leadership styles and the challenges and opportunities identified in special education settings. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) used to measure the linear correlation between two variables. Calculations were conducted using software tools such as Microsoft Excel and SPSS to ensure methodological accuracy and validity.

RESULTS

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered to examine the relationship of challenges and opportunities in the implementation of Special Education in the Schools Division of Camarines Norte.

DISCUSSION

The discussion further evaluates the challenges encountered and the effectiveness of school heads in managing opportunities in SPED implementation using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis. The results show that leadership styles are not significantly related to the challenges faced, but democratic leadership has a significant positive relationship with opportunities in SPED. These findings served as the basis for the development of the **Innovative Interventions for SPED Leadership Implementation**, which aims to strengthen leadership practices, address identified gaps, and promote sustainable and inclusive SPED programs.

Leadership Style of Secondary School Heads in Special Education

Table 1 presents the leadership styles of secondary school principals in special education.

Table 1
Leadership Styles of Secondary School Heads in Special Education

Indicators	Total Score	Rank
A. Authoritative		
1-I'm happy to act as the spokesperson for our group	161	4
2-I'm determined to push projects forward and get results	187	1
3-I am good at organizing other people	176	2
4-I set myself high standards and expect others to do the same for themselves	170	3
B. Democratic		
1-I believe teams work best when everyone is involved in making decisions	190	1
2-I enjoy working on committees	189	2
3-I don't mind how long discussions last, so long as we consider every angle	176	4
4-I think all group members should abide by formal decisions so long as we follow proper procedures	186	3
C. Facilitative		
1-I'm good at bringing out the best in other people	173	3
2-I think people should be allowed to make mistakes to learn	178	2
3-I think the most important thing for a group is the well-being of its member	190	1
4-I love helping other people to develop	190	1
D. Situational		
1-I can take on a leadership role when needed, but I don't consider myself a 'leader'	158	4
2-I'm good at adapting to different situations	182	2
3-I can see situations from many different perspectives	183	1
4-I enjoy role-playing exercises	159	3

Based on the ranking presented in the table, the statement “I’m determined to push projects forward and get results” the highest total score of 187 implies that school heads with an authoritative leadership style are highly goal-driven and focused on achieving outcomes. Northouse (2013), noted that overly directive leadership may limit collaboration and reduce staff motivation. The lowest total score (161) implies that school heads who use an authoritative style may be less comfortable representing or speaking on behalf of their team. Leithwood et al. (2004) noted that authoritative leaders tend to be more directive and may not always prioritize collaborative representation, which can lead to limited participation from staff members. The highest total score of the Democratic Leadership Style is the belief that “teams work best when everyone is involved in making decisions” with score 190 and the lowest indicator under the Democratic Leadership Style is the statement “I don’t mind how long discussions last, so long as we consider every angle,” with a score of 176, implies that school heads practice democracy with time limitations rather than through prolonged deliberation. In the facilitative leadership style, the highest-ranked indicator is “I think the most important thing for a group is the well-being of its members” and “I love helping other people to develop,” each receiving a total score of 190 and the lowest indicator is the statement “I’m good at bringing out the best in other people” (total score of 173). In the context of situational leadership, the highest rated indicator “I can see situations from many different perspectives,” with a total score of 182 and the lowest statement is “I can take on a leadership role when needed, but I don’t consider myself a leader” with score of 158. The results, leadership reflects, empathy, encouragement, and focus on developing people rather than simply directing them.

Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Special Education

Table 2 presents the challenges encountered by secondary school heads in implementing special education, with an overall weighted mean of 3.97, interpreted as Highly Challenging (HC). The lack of adequate learning resource materials for special education (wm = 4.26) is the most critical issue, insufficient teacher training in inclusive education and professional development (wm = 4.18) remains a major challenge. And lastly, limited availability of community resources and support services for students with special needs (wm = 4.18, Highly Challenging) reflects a real and serious problem faced by schools. Aldosiry (2022), emphasized that administrative support and external work conditions are essential for maintaining teacher commitment and reducing stress.

The lowest-rated challenges in the study—though still rated as Highly Challenging—reflect issues that are serious but less urgent than problems like lack of resources or training. “Lack of clear policies, guidelines, or legal frameworks to support inclusive practices” received a weighted mean of 3.58, lack of awareness and understanding of the rights and needs of students with disabilities (wm = 3.70) and resistance or negative attitudes from teachers, staff, parents, or the community toward inclusive practices rated lower than other challenges. (wm = 3.74, still interpreted as Highly Challenging).

To address the challenges in implementing SPED programs, schools should prioritize improving learning resources, enhancing teacher training, engaging the community, clarifying policies, and promoting positive attitudes toward inclusion. Additionally, strong administrative support, as emphasized by Aldosiry (2022), is essential to maintain teacher commitment and ensure effective leadership in managing SPED programs.

Table 2
Challenges Encountered by the School Head
in the Implementation of Special Education

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Lack of adequate learning resource materials for special education	4.26	EC
2. Inadequate budget for specialized support, assistive technologies, or accommodations for diverse learners.	4.16	HC
3. Difficulty in adapting the curriculum to cater to different learning styles and abilities while ensuring that it meets the diverse needs of all students within a mainstream classroom setting	4.12	HC
4. Insufficient teacher training in inclusive education and professional development	4.18	HC
5. Difficulty in accommodating diverse learning needs.	3.90	HC
6. Difficulties in engaging and collaborating with parents or guardians of students with special needs.	3.86	HC
7. Resistance or negative attitudes from teachers, staff, parents, or the community towards inclusive practices.	3.74	HC
8. Lack of clear policies, guidelines, or legal frameworks to support and enforce inclusive education practices at both national and local levels	3.58	HC
9. Students with special needs may experience challenges like being treated differently, feeling isolated, or facing bullying from classmates, which can make it harder for them to be included in the classroom.	3.92	HC
10. Difficulties in assessing and evaluating the progress and achievements of students with diverse needs using appropriate assessment tools and methods tailored for inclusive settings.	3.96	HC
11. Cultural and linguistic barriers in serving diverse populations of students with disabilities.	3.88	HC
12. Limited availability of community resources and support services for students with special needs.	4.18	HC

13. Lack of awareness and understanding of the rights and needs of students with disabilities.	3.70	HC
14. Challenges in implementing individualized education plans (IEPs) effectively.	3.82	HC
15. Insufficient resources and materials for accommodating diverse learning needs.	4.04	HC
16. Inadequate support staff, such as aides and therapists.	4.14	HC
Overall Weighted Mean	3.97	HC

<i>Rating Scale:</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
4.20-5.00	<i>Extremely Challenging (EC)</i>
3.40-4.19	<i>Highly Challenging (HC)</i>
2.60-3.39	<i>Moderately Challenging (MC)</i>
1.80-2.59	<i>Somewhat Challenging (SC)</i>
1.80-2.59	<i>Somewhat Challenging (SC)</i>
1.00-1.79	<i>Not Challenging at all (NC)</i>

Opportunities Associated with School Leadership in Special Education

Table 3 highlights the opportunities associated with school leadership in the implementation of special education, with an overall weighted mean of 4.70, interpreted as Always (A). Most notably, ensuring that special education programs are aligned with the overall goals and priorities of the school (wm = 4.84, A) emerged as the most significant opportunity. In addition, ensuring that students with special needs are included in extracurricular activities and school events (wm = 4.82) reflects the school heads' commitment to holistic inclusion. Moreover, encouraging collaboration and teamwork among teachers to address the individual needs of learners with disabilities (wm = 4.74, A), along with ensuring access to appropriate accommodations and support services (wm = 4.74, A), underscores the importance of collective effort and support systems. These findings are consistent with Buli-Holmberg et al. (2019), who emphasized that collaboration among educators is a key enabling factor in inclusive education. This finding supported by Aldosiry (2022), who noted that when adequate support systems are provided, teachers experience less stress and greater commitment, ultimately benefiting students with diverse needs.

Table 3
Opportunities Associated with Implementation of Special Education

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Score
1. School leaders advocate for inclusive policies and practices in special education.	4.60	Always
2. School leaders facilitate professional development opportunities for special education teachers.	4.60	Always

3. School leaders collaborate with community organizations to provide additional resources and support for students with special needs.	4.62	Always
4. School leaders promote a positive and inclusive school culture that celebrates diversity and supports students with special needs.	4.76	Always
5. School leaders encourage collaboration and teamwork among teachers to address the individual needs of students with disabilities.	4.74	Always
6. School leaders ensure that students with special needs have access to appropriate accommodation and support services.	4.74	Always
7. School leaders allocate resources and funding to support special education programs and initiatives.	4.64	Always
8. School leaders involve parents/guardians in decision-making processes related to their child's special education needs.	4.66	Always
9. School leaders promote a strengths-based approach to supporting students with disabilities.	4.72	Always
10. School leaders foster partnerships with external agencies and organizations to enhance support services for students with special needs.	4.66	Always
11. School leaders collaborate with community organizations to provide additional resources and support for students with special needs.	4.66	Always
12. School leaders promote using assistive technologies and other innovative tools to support students with disabilities in their learning.	4.64	Always
13. School leaders ensure that students with special needs are included in extracurricular activities and school events.	4.82	Always
14. School leaders support the professional growth and development of special education paraprofessionals and support staff.	4.72	Always
15. School leaders promote collaboration and coordination between general education and special education teachers.	4.74	Always
16. School leaders ensure that special education programs are aligned with the overall goals and priorities of the school or district.	4.84	Always
Overall Weighted Mean	4.70	Always

<i>Rating Scale:</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
4.20-5.00	Always
3.40-4.19	Often
2.60-3.39	Sometimes
1.00-1.79	Never
1.80-2.59	Rarely

Relationship between the Leadership Styles and the Challenges Encountered by School Heads and Opportunities Associated with Special Education

Table 4 presents the results of the test for significant relationship between leadership styles of school heads and two variables such as, the challenges they face and the opportunities associated with special education, using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (*r*). The computed correlation coefficients (*r*) and corresponding *p*-values reveal that there are generally weak and statistically insignificant correlations between leadership styles and the challenges encountered by school heads. The obtained *r*-values range from .077 to .192, with all *p*-values greater than the 0.05 level of significance (*p* = .182 to .597). This suggests that no significant relationship exists between the leadership styles of school heads and the challenges they face in implementing or managing special education programs. In other words, the challenges experienced by school heads appear to occur independently of their leadership style.

On the other hand, when considering the opportunities associated with special education, only the democratic leadership style shows a significant positive relationship (*r* = .280, *p* = .046). This correlation, although modest in strength, indicates that school heads who practice a democratic style of leadership tend to perceive or create more opportunities in managing special education programs, particularly on ensuring that special education programs are aligned with the overall goals and priorities of the school or district.

Meanwhile, the authoritative (*r* = .046, *p* = .749), facilitative (*r* = .045, *p* = .758), and situational (*r* = .066, *p* = .648) leadership styles do not show significant relationships with the opportunities associated with special education. These findings suggest that while different leadership approaches may influence management practices, not all of them are directly related to the identification or utilization of opportunities within the special education context.

Table 4
Test for Significant Relationship between the Leadership Styles and the Challenges Encountered by School Heads and Opportunities Associated with Special Education

Leadership Styles	Challenges Faced by School Heads		Opportunities Associated with Special Education	
	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Authoritative	.095	.514	.046	.749
Democratic	.192	.182	.280*	.046
Facilitative	.077	.597	.045	.758
Situational	.100	.491	.066	.648

*Correlation is significant @ 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The findings in Table 4 suggest that the challenges faced by school heads in implementing special education programs are largely independent of their leadership styles. This indicates that these challenges are more deeply rooted in systemic and structural issues such as inadequate funding, lack of specialized personnel, limited resources, and policy constraints. Regardless of whether a school head adopts an authoritative, democratic, facilitative, or situational leadership style, they still encounter similar barriers because these challenges are driven by external factors beyond individual leadership behavior. This implies that addressing special education challenges requires system-wide support and policy reforms, not only changes in leadership style.

However, the finding that democratic leadership positively correlates with opportunities suggests that leadership style does influence how school heads can create or maximize opportunities within the special education context. Democratic leaders tend to encourage participation, collaboration, and shared decision-making, which can lead to more inclusive practices and better integration of SPED programs into the school's overall vision. This implies that while challenges may be unavoidable, democratic leadership can help school heads capitalize on opportunities, especially in aligning special education with school priorities and fostering a supportive environment for learners with special needs. The absence of a significant relationship between leadership styles and the challenges encountered by school heads is supported by Leithwood et al. (2004), who argued that many difficulties in educational leadership are rooted in systemic conditions such as limited funding, policy constraints, and shortages of trained personnel—factors that cannot be easily addressed through leadership style alone.

Similarly, Holmberg Buli et al. (2019) found that although leadership practices and attitudes influence inclusive education, structural and resource-related barriers often outweigh the effects of individual leadership approaches. These studies support the present finding that challenges in special education tend to occur independently of leadership style. On the other hand, the significant positive relationship between democratic leadership and opportunities in special education is corroborated by Ciocon (2022), who emphasized that instructional and collaborative leadership enables school heads to align SPED programs with school-wide goals and priorities, thereby strengthening inclusive practices. Daodaen et al. (2022) also supported this view by noting that principals with positive attitudes toward inclusion and adequate professional preparation are more likely to foster collaboration and shared decision-making, which in turn creates more opportunities for effective SPED implementation.

Conclusions

The study concludes that secondary school heads generally exhibit strong collaborative and supportive leadership styles in special education, particularly through inclusive decision-making, teamwork, and advocacy for learner support. However, while these leadership approaches are evident, there is a need for leadership development programs that strengthen assertive leadership, decision-making, and advocacy skills to further enhance SPED implementation. This suggests that school heads predominantly practice democratic and facilitative leadership in SPED settings, but would benefit from

more training to balance supportive leadership with strong, decisive, and advocacy-driven actions to effectively address SPED challenges and promote inclusive education.

The results suggest that secondary school heads encounter considerable challenges in implementing SPED programs, with the lack of learning materials, inadequate teacher training, and limited funding for assistive technologies as the most critical concerns. These are compounded by insufficient community resources, unclear policies, and social issues such as bullying and exclusion. These findings reflect systemic gaps in support, training, and policy clarity, which hinder the effective implementation of inclusive education. It can be concluded that school leaders exhibit a strong commitment to the implementation and enhancement of SPED programs, as reflected in the high overall weighted mean of 4.70 (Always). The highest opportunities experienced by the respondents include the alignment of SPED programs with broader school goals and priorities (4.84) and the promotion of inclusive participation in extracurricular activities and school events (4.82). These findings demonstrate that school heads are not only focused on academic inclusion but also actively support the holistic development of learners with special needs. Overall, these results affirm that leadership plays a pivotal role in sustaining inclusive practices and ensuring equitable access to quality education for learners with special needs.

The results of the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient analysis indicate that there is no significant relationship between school heads' leadership styles and the challenges in SPED implementation, suggesting that leadership style alone may not be the primary factor influencing difficulties in SPED. However, the analysis also reveals that democratic leadership has a significant positive relationship with the opportunities in SPED implementation, indicating that school heads who practice democratic leadership are more likely to identify and utilize opportunities for improving SPED programs. This implies that while leadership style may not directly influence challenges, it can still enhance the potential for success when combined with other contextual factors. Therefore, other factors such as policy clarity, availability of resources, teacher competencies, stakeholder support, and inclusive school culture may have a stronger impact on the success or difficulties of SPED implementation. These contextual factors, together with democratic leadership, may better explain the effectiveness of SPED programs and the ability to maximize opportunities for learners with special needs.

The proposed intervention plan will enhance the leadership capacity of secondary school principals in implementing and sustaining effective SPED programs. This intervention works by offering targeted training sessions that enhance leadership skills such as democratic decision-making, collaboration, and advocacy, which are essential for inclusive education. It also includes workshops for identifying and solving common SPED challenges such as insufficient learning materials, limited teacher training, and inadequate funding for assistive technologies through effective planning and resource mobilization. Additionally, the intervention promotes collaboration among teachers, parents, and community stakeholders to build stronger support systems and reduce resistance to inclusive practices. By helping principals align SPED goals with the school's overall priorities, the intervention ensures that SPED is integrated into the school's vision

rather than treated as a separate program. Finally, it provides monitoring and evaluation tools that enable school heads to track progress, assess effectiveness, and continuously improve SPED implementation. Overall, the intervention provides a practical and strategic framework that enables school leaders to lead inclusive programs more effectively, address challenges, and maximize opportunities for learners with special needs.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen the leadership capacity of secondary school heads in the implementation of SPED programs. These suggestions aim to address identified challenges, maximize opportunities, and support inclusive practices to ensure that learners with special needs receive quality education and equitable access to school programs.

It is recommended that school heads may be provided with targeted leadership development programs that focus on strengthening their confidence and competence in taking on formal leadership roles and engaging in interactive leadership styles. Training should emphasize strategic decision-making, communication, and inclusive leadership to better support specialized programs such as SPED. Additionally, mentoring and peer learning opportunities may help school leaders model best practices, foster professional growth, and cultivate a stronger sense of accountability and initiative.

Moreover, it is recommended that the Department of Education and school leadership prioritize resource allocation for SPED programs, especially for instructional materials and assistive technologies. Comprehensive and sustained professional development may be provided to teachers to build their competencies in inclusive education. Moreover, clearer policy guidelines and community engagement initiatives may be established to support SPED implementation. Schools may also integrate social-emotional learning (SEL) programs to address bullying, promote inclusivity, and nurture a positive school climate for learners with special needs.

Additionally, it is recommended that school leaders may be continually empowered and recognized for their vital role in advancing inclusive education. Support mechanisms such as leadership training on inclusive strategies, peer collaboration platforms, and incentives for inclusive practices may be institutionalized. Furthermore, policies and programs that strengthen the integration of SPED into all aspects of school life including extracurricular activities, classroom instruction, and school culture may be consistently implemented to sustain inclusive growth. and it is recommended that future interventions and support for SPED implementation go beyond leadership development and focus more on addressing system-level barriers such as improving teacher training, providing adequate instructional materials and assistive technologies, clarifying inclusion policies, and building strong community partnerships. Further research is also encouraged to explore other possible variables such as institutional culture, support systems, or policy implementation fidelity that may better explain variations in SPED implementation outcomes.

Ensure adequate resources and funding for SPED programs, including teacher training, assistive technologies, and instructional materials. Strengthening stakeholder collaboration through advocacy training and policy development. The Schools Division Office (SDO) of Camarines Norte may consider adopting the **Innovative Interventions for SPED Implementation** to provide strategic direction for inclusive education. By implementing these recommendations, school leaders may foster an inclusive and supportive learning environment and ensure equitable educational opportunities for all learners. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies in a wider range of schools to gain broader insights into leadership styles and special education implementation. Using qualitative methods such as interviews or case studies is recommended to gather deeper perspectives from school heads, teachers, parents, and learners. Longitudinal or comparative studies may also be done to examine leadership impacts over time and across different contexts. Finally, researchers are encouraged to design and assess intervention programs that address identified challenges to improve inclusive education practices.

Innovative Interventions for SPED Leadership Implementation

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Department of Education
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PROJECT PROPOSAL

- I. Project Title:** INNOVATIVE INTERVENTIONS FOR SPED LEADERSHIP IMPLEMENTATION
- II. Proponent:** ROSEDEL A. YABA, Teacher III
MaEd in Educational Leadership Student
- III. Time Frame:** August- April, 2025
- IV. Amount Requested:** 3,800.00
- V. Rationale:**

The role of School Leadership in Special Education is pivotal in shaping the landscape of inclusive classrooms. Effective leadership addresses the unique challenges faced by students with special needs and identifies opportunities for creating an inclusive environment. Through proactive measures and strategic decision-making, school leaders can foster a supportive atmosphere that maximizes learning opportunities for all students, ensuring an inclusive educational experience that promotes diversity, equity, and success for every learner (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020).

Implementing a special education program is one of the multifaceted roles that a secondary school principal face. A school principal should ensure that learners with special needs receive quality and equitable education. As school leaders, they should be equipped with essential strategies, best practices, and practical tools to enhance their leadership in implementing the special education program.

In the study that I conducted, I found that the school leadership style and the challenges and opportunities in implementing the special education program have no significant relationship. This suggests that while leadership is a crucial factor, other elements, such as teacher preparedness, administrative support, curriculum adaptability, and community involvement, play significant roles in successful implementation.

To address these challenges, an intervention plan, **Innovative Interventions for SPED Implementation**, is being proposed based on insights from international and local

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studies. Research by De Matthews et al. (2021), Nordin et al. (2020), and Aldosiry (2022) emphasize the importance of effective leadership, administrative support, and workload management in improving special education outcomes. Similarly, Sun & Xin (2020) and Burwell (2022) highlight the need for proper training for school leaders to oversee inclusive education effectively. Local studies such as Clocon (2022) and Daodaoen et al. (2022) confirm that instructional leadership and professional experience directly influence SPED program implementation.

I. PROPOSED ACTIVITIES FOR SY 2025-2026

A. Leadership Development and Capacity Building

1. Propose a specialized training programs on SPED leadership, focusing on:
 - o Inclusive Leadership and decision-making
 - o Advocacy Strategies for Special Education
 - o Legal and Policy Frameworks for SPED implementation
2. Establish mentorship programs where experienced school heads can guide new leaders in SPED management.
 - o Peer Learning and Mentorship Program
 - School heads will be paired with experienced SPED leaders to share the best practices.
3. Strengthening Action Research & Innovation Grants
 - o School leaders will be encouraged to develop innovative SPED programs with funding support from DepEd or external partners.

B. Resource and Budget Allocation

1. Ensure dedicated funding for SPED programs, including teacher training, assistive technologies, and learning materials.
2. Advocate for government support to increase financial investment in SPED resources.
3. Develop a monitoring mechanism to track and evaluate resource utilization and effectiveness.
4. Establish a SPED Resource Hub. A centralized database for:
 - o Teaching and learning materials
 - o Assistive technology resources

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- o Sample Individualized Education Plan (IEP) templates
 - Special Education Teacher Capacity-Building
 - 5. Conduct modular training workshops on:
 - o Inclusive teaching strategies
 - o Adaptive curriculum design
 - o Behavioral and emotional support
 - 6. Offering Scholarships & Professional Development Opportunities
 - o School heads & teachers will have access to certification courses and scholarships for SPED specialization.
- PROPOSED ACTIVITIES FOR SY 2026-2027**
- C. Policy and Legal Strengthening**
1. Align school policies with national and international SPED laws to ensure compliance and inclusivity.
 - Develop school-level policy guidelines to support SPED implementation.
 2. Establish clear guidelines for implementing inclusive education, including the roles of school heads and teachers.
 3. Regularly review and update policies to address emerging issues and trends in SPED.
- D. Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration**
1. Strengthen collaboration with parents, community leaders, and external organizations to support SPED initiatives.
 - a. Parent and Community Partnership Program
 - o Establish Parent Support Groups to engage families in special education.
 - o Strengthen collaboration with local government, NGOs, and universities for resources & funding.
 - SPED Advocacy & Awareness Campaign
 - o Conduct awareness drives, inclusive education forums, and community events to promote acceptance and reduce stigma.
 - Policy Development & Funding Initiatives
 2. Encourage partnerships with universities, NGOs, and research institutions to enhance SPED training and professional development.
 3. Conduct awareness campaigns to foster positive attitudes toward inclusive education within school communities.
 - o Conduct awareness drives, inclusive education forums, and community events

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to promote acceptance and reduce stigma.

- o Advocate for budget allocation for assistive technologies and enhanced funding for SPED programs.

E. Monitoring, Evaluation, and Accountability

1. Develop a standardized evaluation tool to assess the effectiveness of leadership approaches in SPED.
2. Establish feedback mechanisms to involve teachers, parents, and students in policy improvement efforts.
 Recognize and reward exemplary leadership practices in SPED to encourage continuous improvement.

1. Short-Term (1-2 Years)

- o Develop and pilot leadership training programs.
- o Establish funding and resource allocation mechanisms.
- o Initiate partnerships with stakeholders.
- o Strengthen policy implementation and enforcement.
- o Continuously improve SPED policies based on research and feedback.

A.1. Date of Conduct:

Aug 2025-April 2026
 May 2026-April 2027

A.2. Duration of Activity:

School Year 2025-2026
 School Year 2026-2027

A.3. Venue/Platform:

All activities will be held through face-to-face sessions.

A.4. Target Participants:

All public secondary school heads. Internal and external stakeholders of education.

This intervention plan is designed to enhance the leadership capacity of secondary school principals in implementing and sustaining effective Special Education (SPED) programs. Anchored on relevant leadership theories, inclusive education principles, and evidence-based practices learned through higher education, the proposed strategies and activities are designed to address identified gaps in leadership approaches.

Based on research findings, the plan targets key challenges and increases opportunities in SPED implementation. It provides a strategic direction to build an

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Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Region V – Bicol
Division of Camarines Norte
SAN LORENZO RUIZ NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
San Lorenzo Ruiz, Camarines Norte

Accomplishment Report
Documentation

POST IMPLEMENTATION

I. Strategies

Monitoring and evaluation of tool's effectiveness

II. Description

Develop a standardized evaluation tool to assess the effectiveness of leadership approaches in Special Education (SPED) programs.

Establish inclusive feedback mechanisms that actively involve teachers, parents, and students in identifying areas for policy and program improvement.

Implement a recognition and incentive system to honor exemplary leadership practices in SPED, thereby promoting a culture of continuous improvement and excellence.

III. Resource Needed

Human

- Project Owner/Proponent
- School Head
- PSDS
- Materials
- Bond paper
- Ink
- Printer
- Evaluation forms
- Feedback tools

IV. Indicator Success

Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting.

A.8. Resource Requirement

Resources needed in this project shall be charged to MOOE, SPTA, donations from external stakeholders.

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to promote acceptance and reduce stigma.

- o Advocate for budget allocation for assistive technologies and enhanced funding for SPED programs.

E. Monitoring, Evaluation, and Accountability

1. Develop a standardized evaluation tool to assess the effectiveness of leadership approaches in SPED.
2. Establish feedback mechanisms to involve teachers, parents, and students in policy improvement efforts.

Recognize and reward exemplary leadership practices in SPED to encourage continuous improvement.

1. Short-Term (1-2 Years)

- o Develop and pilot leadership training programs.
- o Establish funding and resource allocation mechanisms.
- o Initiate partnerships with stakeholders.
- o Strengthen policy implementation and enforcement.
- o Continuously improve SPED policies based on research and feedback.

A.1. Date of Conduct:

Aug 2025-April 2026
May 2026-April 2027

A.2. Duration of Activity:

School Year 2025-2026
School Year 2026-2027

A.3. Venue/Platform:

All activities will be held through face-to-face sessions.

A.4. Target Participants:

All public secondary school heads. Internal and external stakeholders of education.

This intervention plan is designed to enhance the leadership capacity of secondary school principals in implementing and sustaining effective Special Education (SPED) programs. Anchored on relevant leadership theories, inclusive education principles, and evidence-based practices learned through higher education, the proposed strategies and activities are designed to address identified gaps in leadership approaches.

Based on research findings, the plan targets key challenges and increases opportunities in SPED implementation. It provides a strategic direction to build an

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inclusive, equitable, and supportive learning environment for learners with special needs. By equipping school leaders with the appropriate tools, competencies, and frameworks, this intervention seeks to ensure the long-term success and institutionalization of SPED in secondary schools.

A.5. Objectives:

- Strengthening the capacity of school principals in decision-making, advocacy, and resource management for special education.
- Address the challenges in special education implementation through policy enhancements, funding allocation, and capacity-building initiatives.
- Promote an inclusive and equitable learning environment for all students.

A.6. Expected Output:

The **Innovative Interventions for SPED Implementation** aims to address identified challenges through leadership capacity-building, teacher training, policy development, and resource mobilization to enhance the effectiveness of special education in inclusive classrooms.

A.7. Methodology:

PRE-IMPLEMENTATION

I. Strategies

Preparation and submission of action plan for approval of SDO.

II. Description

The implementation of the strategy shall begin with the preparation of a comprehensive action plan by the designated program owner or proponent. This action plan must clearly outline the proposed activities, objectives, timelines, resource requirements, and expected outputs aligned with the program's overall goals.

Once completed, the action plan shall be reviewed and endorsed by the school head. It will then be formally submitted to the Schools Division Office (SDO) for review, evaluation, and approval.

Upon SDO approval, the program team shall proceed with the execution of the activities as scheduled, ensuring close coordination with involved committees, stakeholders, and beneficiaries.

Monitoring and documentation will be conducted throughout the implementation to assess progress and guide adjustments when necessary.

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- SPED Advocacy & Awareness Campaign
- Conduct awareness drives, inclusive education forums, and community events to promote acceptance and reduce stigma.
- Policy Development & Funding Initiatives
Encourage partnerships with universities, NGOs, and research institutions to enhance SPED training and professional development.
Conduct awareness campaigns to foster positive attitudes toward inclusive education within school communities.
- Conduct awareness drives, inclusive education forums, and community events to promote acceptance and reduce stigma.
- Advocate for budget allocation for assistive technologies and enhanced funding for SPED programs.

Monitoring, Evaluation, and Accountability

Develop a standardized evaluation tool to assess the effectiveness of leadership approaches in SPED.

Establish feedback mechanisms to involve teachers, parents, and students in policy improvement efforts.

Recognize and reward exemplary leadership practices in SPED to encourage continuous improvement.

III.B.Resource Needed

Human

- Project Owner/Proponent
- School Head

PSDS

Materials

- Bond paper
- Ink
- Printer

IV.Indicator Success

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Total	P 3,800.00
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Note: This project proposal is respectfully submitted for perusal and consideration as part of the researcher's graduate thesis requirements.

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Reviewed by:

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Secondary School Principal I

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Recommending Approval:

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APPROVED: By the Authority of the SDS

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declare that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and they were fully informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, and all data were handled in accordance with applicable data privacy regulations. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the research process. The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and the research was conducted and reported without bias. The findings and results were used solely for academic and research purposes. Additionally, any use of artificial intelligence tools in the preparation of this study has been fully disclosed.

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